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LABORATORY TEST INDICATORS AS A PREDICTOR OF THE SEVERITY OF COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic that is developing every day, doctors need methods that can accurately assess the severity of the disease, predictors, and the effectiveness of treatment. These tools should not only have high sensitivity and specificity, but also be affordable, economical and easy to use. The article discusses the scientific work of regional and foreign researchers on the relationship between the severity of the course of coronavirus infection and laboratory blood tests.

Keywords: Coronavirus infection, laboratory tests, complete blood tests, severity of COVID-19.

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ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ ПРИ COVID-19 КАК ПРЕДИКТОР СТЕПЕНИ ТЯЖЕСТИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В условиях развивающейся с каждым днём COVID-19 пандемии, врачи нуждаются в методах, способных с высокой точностью оценивать тяжесть заболевания, предикторов, эффективность проводимого лечения. Эти инструменты должны не только обладать высокой чувствительностью и специфичностью, но и быть доступными, экономичными и удобными в применении. В статье рассмотрены научные работы региональных и зарубежных исследователей посвящённых взаимосвязи тяжести течения коронавирусной инфекции и лабораторными анализами крови.

Ключевые слова: Коронавирусная инфекция, лабораторные анализы, общий анализ крови, степень тяжести COVID-19.

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COVID-19 OG'IRLIK DARAJASINI BASHORATLASHDA LABORATOR KO'RSATKICHLARNING AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Kundan kunga rivojlanib borayotgan yangi koronavirus infeksiyasi pandemiyasi sharoitida shifokorlarga kasallikning og'irligini, prognozini va davolash samaradorligini aniq baholay oladigan usullar kerak. Ushbu vositalar nafaqat yuqori sezuvchanlik va o'ziga xoslikka ega bo'lishi, balki arzon,

tejamkor va foydalanish uchun qulay bo'lishi kerak. Maqolada mahalliy va chet el ilmiy izlanuvchilarning koronavirus infeksiyasining og'irlik darajalari va qon laborator tahlillari orasidagi o'zaro bog'liqligiga bag'ishlangan ilmiy ishlari o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Koronavirus infeksiyasi, laborator tahlil, umumiy qon tahlili, COVID-19 og'irlik darajasi.

Introduction. The widespread spread of the new coronavirus infection requires the search for clinical and laboratory predictors of disease progression, severe forms, and mortality. The development of predictive indicators, risk stratification, and timely delivery of the necessary care to patients at high risk of developing a severe disease and optimizing the allocation of limited human and technical resources in the context of an ongoing pandemic. . In addition, the identification of laboratory parameters that distinguish severe and non-severe cases, as well as cases with a high or low risk of death, will significantly improve not only the patient's condition, but also clinical treatment protocols [3, 4].

The purpose of the study: To study the relationship between general blood test results and the severity of COVID-19.

Among the potential predictors of disease severity according to the obtained data, a number of indicators related to severe COVID-19 and negative consequences of the disease were identified. Close regularities were found in the isolated groups. Notably, the authors were able to identify a number of differences between the cohorts of patients with severe disease and those who died from COVID-19. In seriously ill patients, the number of leukocyte cells increased slightly (up to $0.41 \times 10^9 / l$ on average), and in patients who died, this indicator increased significantly (on average, $4.15 \times 10^9 / l$ up to 1). Thus, in patients with severe disease, a significant increase in leukocytes is associated with clinical deterioration and the possibility of bacterial infection.

It is noteworthy that an increase in the number of leukocytes is associated with an increase in the content of neutrophils, as the opposite trend was observed for lymphocytes, monocytes and eosinophils. In addition, CD4 and CD8 populations are reduced in patients with severe disease. It has been assumed that the survival of patients is directly related to the ability of the body to replenish lymphocytes killed by the virus [7]. However, the accuracy of these predictors has not been sufficiently studied to date. In addition, many diseases and conditions commonly seen in patients with COVID-19 affect peripheral blood leukocyte levels. See makes it difficult to use this diagnostic and prognostic sign alone in many difficult clinical situations. In this study, the level of leukocytes at admission was not significantly related to the severity of the patients' condition.

Taking into account the above, it is necessary to search for new clinical and laboratory indicators of severity and prognosis of COVID-19. These markers should have high sensitivity and specificity, and should be available and easy to use for detection in hospitals of any level. As one of these markers, the erythrocyte cell size distribution width (RDW) can be used, (an indicator of the range of variation of red blood cells in their size) - a measure that shows how equal the size of red blood cells in the blood is. Usually, RDW measures changes in erythrocyte volume and its heterogeneity index. Is required for measurement and is used together with various laboratory analyzes for differential diagnosis of diseases of the hematological system [8]. A patient with RDW above the normal range probably reflects the presence of anisocytosis associated with the presence of small or large erythrocytes, a decrease in the value of this indicator, as a rule, is not clinically significant [9]. Recent studies show that the determination of RDW is important in patients with diabetes, cardiovascular disease, infectious diseases, and cancer [8, 10]. Wang An-Yi et al. (2018) convincingly demonstrated in their study that RDW is an independent predictor of mortality in elderly patients with sepsis. Besides, high RDW levels can be used as a marker of poor outcomes in patients with a sepsis-related organ failure (qSOFA) score of less than 2 [11]. Similar results have been shown in studies by other authors, confirming the possibility of using RDW as a prognostic marker to evaluate the 28-day survival of patients with severe sepsis or septic shock [12, 13]. It should be noted that the same data were obtained for neonatal sepsis [14, 15]. However, further studies on larger randomized groups are needed to confirm the findings. similar results were shown in studies by other

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A number of studies have shown that an informative criterion for identifying patients with severe forms of novel coronavirus infection is the level of lymphocytes in the general blood test [18]. In this study, lower levels of lymphocytes and higher levels of neutrophils were associated with a more severe course of COVID-19. However, the neutrophil-lymphocyte index (N/L), which is calculated by dividing the absolute number of neutrophils by the absolute number of lymphocytes [19], has been shown to be most associated with the severity of clinical symptoms and the level of C-reactive protein. According to a number of authors, this indicator reflects not only the severity of inflammation, but also the severity of the disease by more than 3 units. with its growth, it also predicts the possibility of an unpleasant clinical course of the disease [10, 11], and a direct correlation with lung damage in MSCT is determined: $r=0.823$; $p<0.001$ [12].

Summary. Monitoring the above parameters during hospitalization can be useful in evaluating the effectiveness of therapy. The presented data can be the basis for creating a cheap and cost-effective way to assess the severity of COVID-19 and the effectiveness of treatment in real clinical practice.

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